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DELIVERABLE REPORT

DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION PLAN - UPDATED VERSION DELIVERABLE: D21

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Abstract:

The dissemination and exploitation plan has been updated in line with the review recommendation. The distinction between stakeholders, policymakers, and financial decision makers is now clearly defined, with tailored communication goals for each audience. A structured audience differentiation matrix maps definitions, channels, and objectives. LinkedIn is explicitly positioned as a professional networking and stakeholder hub, while YouTube is introduced as the primary vehicle for engaging the general public, students, and educators. Established dissemination channels in particle physics (CERN ATS Newsletter, CERN Courier) are also integrated to reinforce credibility and embed project results within the broader scientific community. This revised strategy ensures

that dissemination activities are well aligned with established practices and the specific needs of distinct audiences.

MuCol Consortium, 2025

For more information on MuCol, its partners and contributors please see <https://mucol.web.cern.ch/>

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Delivery Slip

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1. INTRODUCTION

The communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy has been revised in line with the review recommendations. In particular, the distinction between stakeholders and financial decision makers has been clarified.

Stakeholders comprise the broad group of actors with an institutional or professional link to the project (e.g. research institutions, industry partners, international organisations, policymakers, general public). Financial decision makers represent the narrower group with direct influence over resources and budget allocations (e.g. EU funding bodies, national ministries, private sector executives).

Communication activities are targeted accordingly: stakeholders are addressed through transparency, community-building and engagement via the website, LinkedIn, and embedded contributions in established channels. Financial decision makers, by contrast, require concise, outcome-oriented communication that highlights impact, efficiency, and alignment with strategic priorities.

Traditional dissemination outlets in particle physics remain essential. LinkedIn has proven to be an effective professional hub during the first year, establishing a community of approximately 500 relevant followers. However, since it has limited resonance with the wider public, YouTube will now be introduced as a central platform, particularly for educational purposes and younger audiences. The project website continues to serve as the authoritative reference for news, reports, and official updates.

Instagram has not been prioritised at this stage, as effective use depends on a continuous flow of visually compelling content. This option may be revisited once prototypes and demonstrators are available.

Taken together, this approach ensures that dissemination and exploitation activities remain aligned with established practices in high-energy physics while addressing the distinct needs of diverse audiences.

2. STRATEGIC NARRATIVE

Our communication strategy rests on three complementary pillars: the project website, LinkedIn, and YouTube. Each channel serves specific audiences and objectives, while together they provide broad reach, professional credibility, and visibility to the general public.

- Website: the authoritative reference point for news, reports, and long-term transparency.
- LinkedIn: the central hub for stakeholder engagement, professional networking, and amplification of project activities.
- YouTube: the primary vehicle to reach the wider public, younger audiences, and education-oriented communities through accessible visual content.

This channel mix reflects both established practices in particle physics dissemination and the need to extend communication beyond the scientific community.

3. REVIEW OF YEAR 1 – LINKEDIN FOCUS

In the first year, LinkedIn was deliberately prioritised as the main channel. The objective was to establish a professional community of industry representatives, research partners, and international organisations – groups crucial for the early stages of the project.

Results:

- Community of ~500 followers established.
- Strong engagement (likes, shares, comments).
- Extended reach through shares beyond direct networks.
- Followers include representatives from industry, research organisations, and international bodies.

LinkedIn has proven highly effective for stakeholder communication and professional credibility. While it is not designed for the general public, its role as the project’s central hub remains crucial: it provides timely, credible updates visible to stakeholders, partners, and multipliers who further disseminate content.

4. CHANNEL STRATEGY

The project’s dissemination channels are designed to complement each other. The website functions as the official and authoritative reference point for all project-related information. LinkedIn serves as the central hub for stakeholder engagement and professional networking, enabling the project to build credibility and strengthen its community. YouTube is being introduced to broaden outreach and serve as the main vehicle for engaging the general public and education-focused audiences.

At this stage, our communication priorities are better served by platforms that:

- Directly engage professional stakeholders and decision-makers (**LinkedIn**),
- Provide educational depth and broad accessibility (**YouTube**),
- Ensure authoritative reference and transparency (**Website**).

In addition to these core channels, the project benefits from established communication structures in the particle physics community, such as the CERN Accelerator and Technology Sector (ATS) Newsletter and the CERN Courier. Contributions to such outlets ensure that results are embedded in the broader dissemination ecosystem and reach specialized audiences effectively.

Channel	Target Audience	Content Types	Objective
LinkedIn	Industry, scientific community, international organizations, stakeholders	Updates, event highlights, partner news	Central hub for stakeholders, strengthen community, build credibility
YouTube	General public, students, educators, younger audiences	Explainer videos, project profiles, educational material	Broaden outreach, make science accessible, support education
Website	General public, stakeholders, policymakers, media	News, reports, project updates, press releases	Authoritative reference, transparency, long-term accessibility
Collaboration with established outlets	Scientific community, policymakers	CERN ATS Newsletter, CERN Courier: highlights, milestones, updates	Reach specialized audiences, reinforce credibility

5. AUDIENCE DIFFERENTIATION

The project addresses a diverse set of audiences, each requiring tailored communication. This approach responds directly to the review recommendation to clarify distinctions between stakeholders and financial decision makers.

- **Stakeholders** form the broadest group, encompassing all those with a professional or institutional connection to the project. They may not directly fund or regulate activities but benefit from its progress and enhance its visibility and credibility.
- **Policymakers** shape the political and regulatory framework and require clear evidence that the project aligns with EU and national science policy priorities.
- **Financial decision makers** represent a narrower group within the stakeholder community, focused specifically on budget allocations and measurable impacts. Their information needs are concise and outcome-driven, emphasising efficiency, accountability, and demonstrable results.
- **Scientific community** requires open access to results, opportunities for collaboration, and integration into the wider research ecosystem through conferences, workshops, and open-access repositories such as arXiv and Zenodo.

- **General public** represents the widest audience. Communication must simplify scientific content, visualise concepts, and emphasise educational outreach.

Audience	Definition	Examples	Channel(s)	Goals
Stakeholders	Broad group with a professional or institutional interest	Industry partners, international organizations, research infrastructures	LinkedIn, website	Build awareness, foster collaboration, ensure transparency
Policymakers	Influence science policy	European Commission, national ministries	Website, LinkedIn, direct meetings	Demonstrate alignment with research and policy goals
Financial decision makers	Control budgets and funding allocations	Funding agencies, research councils	Reports, KPI presentations, website	Demonstrate impact, justify funding, ensure accountability
Scientific community	Advance scientific knowledge and technical prototypes	Researchers, physicists	Conferences, workshops, publications, LinkedIn, Website	Knowledge sharing, collaboration, dissemination of results
General public	No scientific background	Society at large, students, teachers	YouTube, LinkedIn	Increase scientific knowledge, inspire interest in research

This mapping ensures that each audience receives communication tailored to its needs: concise and impact-oriented for policymakers and founders, open and integrative for the scientific community, and accessible and inspiring for the wider public.

6. YOUTUBE

YouTube has been selected as the next key dissemination channel. As the world's largest video platform, it combines broad demographic reach with strong educational potential. Its content can be embedded in websites, presentations, and social media, increasing both visibility and reusability. This makes YouTube a powerful tool not only for the general public but also for students, teachers, and younger audiences less active on professional networks such as LinkedIn.

In contrast, Instagram has not been prioritised at this stage. The platform's effectiveness depends heavily on a steady flow of highly visual material such as prototypes, animations, or demonstrators, which are not yet available in sufficient quality or quantity. For the current phase, communication goals are better served through LinkedIn, YouTube, and the project website. Once tangible

demonstrators are available, Instagram may be reconsidered as an amplification channel for visual storytelling.

